

Synthesis and optical characterization of Yttrium doped Cerium Oxide Nanoparticles

R.Thirumamagal¹, S.Nivetha², K.Kaviyarasu³, **A.Ayeshamariam**^{1,2*}, M.Valanarasu⁴, and M.Jayachandran⁵

¹Research and Development Centre, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, 641 046, India

²Department of Physics, Khadir Mohideen College, Adirampattinam. 614 701, India

³Nanosciences African network (NANOAFNET), Materials Research Group (MRG), iThemba LABS-National Research Foundation (NRF), 1 Old Faure Road, 7129, P O Box 722, Somerset West, Western Cape Province, South Africa.

⁴Addiriyah Chair for Environmental Studies, Department of Botany and Microbiology, College of Science, King Saud University, P.O. Box 2455, Riyadh 11451, Saudi Arabia

⁵Department of Physics, Sethu Institute of Technology, Pullor, Kariapatti, 625 116, India

Corresponding author Email: aismma786@gmail.com

Abstract

In bio synthesis, boiling method is used to prepare Yttrium doped Cerium Oxide nanoparticles. Dates syrup (10 ml), Neem leaves extract of 10 ml was added to prepare this nanoparticles. Neem leaves extract and dates syrup which are acting as a reducing agent of Cerium Nitrate source material. Bio synthesized Yttrium doped Cerium Oxide was characterized by using X-Ray Diffractometer to confirm crystalline nature and structure of the nanoparticles. Scanning Electron Microscopy and Elemental X-Ray analysis was carried out to confirm the presence of metals in the nanoparticles. Magnetic studies explained the intensity of magnetization of the sample (emu/g) and coercivity of the sample. These magnetic studies were analysed by using Vibrating Sample Magnetometer. Bio activity of the samples were analysed from the studies of Anti bacterial and Anti fungal.

Keywords: Bio synthesis, Neem leaves, XRD, Anti bacterial, Antifungal

References

- [1]. Sun, C et al., *Nanotechnology*, 16(9), (2005), 1454.
- [2]. Yan, L et al., *Crystal Growth and Design*, 8(5), (2008), 1474-1477.